

Advances in Functionalization of Polymer supports for Synthesis and Modification of Oligonucleotides

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With the advent of commercial applications in biotechnology the economic importance of oligonucleotides including linkers, adaptors, primers etc. and the starting materials for their synthesis such as the nucleosides, the nucleotides and the basic reagents and chemicals required for their modifications has enhanced enormously. In monetary terms, they contribute in our estimate to nearly the equivalent of US\$ 0.2 billion in global business. The main users of the whole range are the U.S., Europe, Japan, Canada and Australia, but the consumption in the developing countries especially in Asia, South American countries and Cuba is increasing fast.

The foundation for the synthesis of oligonucleotides was laid with the unravelling of the double helical structure of DNA by Watson and Crick in 1953¹. In 1955, Michelson and Todd² reported the first synthesis of a dinucleotide containing a natural 3'-5' phosphodiester linkage by the chemical method (Scheme 1). Almost concurrently Hall *et al.*³ demonstrated the development of a

Scheme 1. Michelson and Todd's phosphotriester approach.

new strategy based on the formation of H-phosphonate intermediate for the synthesis of phosphodiester linked dinucleotide (Scheme 2). Khorana *et al.*⁴ succeeded in developing a new condensing reagent for the formation

Scheme 2. Hall's H-phosphonate approach.

of internucleotide linkage, popularly known as the phosphodiester method of synthesis (Scheme 3). This approach led to the total synthesis of a biologically ac-

Scheme 3. Khorana's phosphodiester approach.

tive gene for tyrosine suppressor tRNA⁵⁻⁷. Subsequently, after the introduction of new phosphorylating and coupling reagents⁸⁻¹⁸, the phosphotriester approach (Scheme 4) became an alternative to the phosphodiester method. Letsinger *et al.*^{19,20} brought a revolution in oligonucleotide synthesis by taking advantage of highly reactive

Scheme 4. Modified phosphotriester approach.

trivalent phosphorus analogs for the rapid formation of internucleotide bonds. This procedure was further modified by Beaucage and Caruthers²¹ to enable the use of a new class of intermediates, deoxyribonucleoside phosphoramidites. The method played a key role in the automation of DNA synthesis by using solid phase supports that gave rise to the introduction of automated gene machines for the assembly of oligonucleotides upto the length of over 200-300 bases and occasionally even larger. Progress in these synthetic methods have been reviewed from time to time²²⁻²⁷.

Solid phase supported synthesis of oligonucleotides

Polymer supported synthesis which is also known as the solid phase supported synthesis brought in greater maneuverity and wider manipulativity of oligonucleotides. This also led to the quicker availability of a varied range of oligonucleotides. The concept was first proposed by Merrifield²⁸⁻³⁰ in the context of peptide synthesis. He demonstrated this new technique by carrying out the reaction wherein one of the reactants was reversibly and covalently bound to an inert insoluble solid polymeric material. Chain elongation was effected from the bound reactant. The support-bound product could subsequently be released by appropriate cleavage conditions. The usefulness of this technique is especially for the assembly of oligomers and polymers of known sequences by the stepwise sequential addition of chemically related monomers.

Efforts of Letsinger and Mahadevan^{8,31} led to design of a synthesis strategy for a trinucleotide on a polymeric material soon after the introduction of the novel concept introduced for the synthesis of peptides. Following its introduction, continuous improvements in various facets of the synthetic steps have brought this concept to the stage^{21,32,33} of such developments that even the non-chemist actual users could now synthesize these complex oligomers without much difficulties. In Scheme 5,

we summarize schematically the updated developments in polymer supported synthesis of oligonucleotides.

Advantages of solid phase supported synthesis strategy

The solid phase strategy has a number of advantages over the conventional solution phase synthesis : (a) the polynucleotide chain remains bound to the support throughout the course of chain elongation, (b) no stepwise separation, purification and characterization of the intermediates is required, (c) large excess of the reagents employed to force the reaction to completion can easily be washed off, and the desired product can be obtained in high yields, and (d) repetition of similar or identical steps allow to automate the solid phase synthesis.

Solid phase synthesis – main features

The main features of solid phase synthesis of oligonucleotides via phosphoramidite chemistry comprise the following : (i) selection of a polymer support, (ii) functionalization of support to generate reactive groups, (iii) protection of functional groups in the monomeric units, (iv) attachment of the leader nucleoside to the polymer support, (v) blocking of underivatized functional groups on the support, (vi) removal of the protecting groups from terminal hydroxyl moiety, (vii) coupling with a suitable

Scheme 5. Solid phase synthesis of oligonucleotides via phosphoramidite approach.

protected monomer in the presence of a catalyst, (viii) capping of unreacted groups, (ix) oxidation of phosphite triester to phosphotriester moiety, (x) repetition of steps vi to ix until desired length of an oligomer is obtained, (xi) cleavage from support and removal of protecting groups, and (xii) purification and characterization.

Choice of polymer support

The choice of polymer support plays the most important role in the solid phase synthesis of oligonucleotides. Solid phase oligonucleotide synthesis^{8,31} was demonstrated in 1965; however, due to the non-availability of appropriate polymer support, it took nearly two decades to popularize this method. Currently several support materials have been known, some of which are routinely used in oligonucleotide synthesis as listed in Table 1.

As the successful completion of synthesis of oligomers depends upon both the physical and chemical properties of polymer supports, an ideal material must fulfil the following criteria : (i) support should have uniform surface with appropriate pore size to contain the desired oligomer, (ii) particle size should be uniform, (iii) it should have appreciable mechanical strength and should be non-friable or non-fragile, and (iv) it should be non-

swellable in organic solvents.

Because not so satisfactory results are encountered in certain situations with several of the supports listed in Table 1, efforts were made to concentrate on silica based supports, as this material was thought to possess the most of the desired properties and was considered suitable to be developed further. The first report on the silica gel was published by Köster³⁷ in 1972 following phosphodiester approach; the support was found to be useful after the phosphite triester chemistry was applied to solid phase synthesis of oligonucleotides. In spite of rigid and non-swellable nature of the silica, the non-uniformity of particles and its fragile nature (which is prone to fragmentation) had restricted its use. Subsequently, this was superseded by another silica based support, commonly known as controlled pore glass (CPG). CPG supports in conjunction with phosphoramidite approach are currently the most widely used polymer supports for the synthesis of oligonucleotides. Unlike silica gel, CPG has certain properties which makes it a universal carrier of choice : (i) CPG supports are non-friable under all conditions therefore easy in handling particularly during process of functionalization and synthesis, (ii) these are incompress-

TABLE 1—ORGANIC AND INORGANIC POLYMER SUPPORTS EMPLOYED FOR OLIGONUCLEOTIDE SYNTHESIS

Nature of polymer support	Property	Ref.
Polystyrene (0% crosslinked)	Non-polar, soluble, swellable	34, 35
Polystyrene (Popcorn) (1% crosslinked)	Non-polar, insoluble, mechanically stable	8, 36
Polyethylene glycol	Polar, soluble, insoluble in org. solvent	37–41
Polyvinyl alcohol	Polar, soluble, insoluble in org. solvent	42, 43
Vinylacetate- <i>N</i> -vinylpyrrolidone copolymer	Polar, soluble, insoluble in org. solvent	44
Sephadex LH 20	Polar, hydrophilic and lipophilic character	45
Polyamide	Polar, swellable, insoluble, mechanically stable	46, 47
Poly-L-lysine	Polar	48
Kieselguhr-polyamide	Polar, mechanically stable, insoluble, non-swellable	49
Cellulose/paper disc	Polar, non-swellable, flexible	50–56
Silica gel	Irregular sized rigid particles, polar, insoluble, non-swellable	33, 57–61
Controlled pore glass	Rigid structure, polar, insoluble, incompressible, non-swellable, available in various pore sizes	62–64
Polystyrene-polyethylene glycol (PEG-PS) (Tentacle)	Swellable, uniform sized beads	65, 66
Polystyrene (50% crosslinked)	Non-polar, non-swellable, non-porous rigid beads, mechanically stable	67
Polytetrafluoroethylene-polystyrene copolymer	Mechanical stability, non-swellable, hydrophobic	69–71
Poly(<i>N</i> -acryloylmorpholine) (PACM)	Polar, soluble in org. solvents	72

sible for obtaining constant flow rates in continuous flow system, (iii) these are extremely useful for small scale synthesis on automated synthesizers, (iv) CPG supports are available in a variety of pore sizes, viz. 350, 500, 1400 and 3000 Å, and (v) unlike polystyrene and polyamide supports, the accessibility of functional groups on the support is solvent-independent.

More recently developed supports based on uniform pore size and shape have further augmented and eased the oligonucleotide synthesis. And it is now possible that using these supports one can get >99.5% coupling yields, thereby making the purification unnecessary for most of the biological applications.

Effect of pore size

Another crucial feature of the polymer supported synthesis of oligonucleotide which influences the yields and purity of the synthetic oligomers when longer chains are to be assembled is the pore size of the solid support⁷³⁻⁷⁵. The pore size is almost inversely proportional to the surface area. Total surface area is the area available for the functionalization process. In other words, the amount of nucleosides loaded on to the support decreases with increase in pore size. Conceptually, this means that smaller area is available for derivatization for larger pore sized polymer support. The effect of pore size on the synthesis of longer oligomers was studied by Katzhendlar *et al.*⁷³ and Aerschot *et al.*⁷⁴. They established the importance of this factor by carrying out three different experiments, namely, (i) the quantitative determination of support functionalization by 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane which provides the estimation of silanol groups on the surface of different supports with different pore sizes, (ii) adsorption of a dye molecule on the surface of the polymer supports which accounts for the porosity of the surface and relatively free area available for binding, and (iii) the use of scanning electron microscopy for the determination of surface structure. Furthermore, they synthesized a large number of oligonucleotides with varying chain lengths from where they observed that the coupling efficiency abruptly dropped when the synthesis of oligomer longer than 50–60 bases were attempted on CPG with pore size of 500 Å. They concluded that increasing length of oligomers may be responsible for enhancing steric hindrances around the pores which substantially reduced the passage of the reagents.

Nature and length of the spacer

The efficiency of synthesis and purity of the final product depend upon the nature and the length of the spacer

arm separating the leader nucleoside from the support. The crowding near the surface of the polymer support (steric hindrance) could be reduced if the length of the chain connecting the nucleoside is increased which would enhance the accessibility of the leader nucleoside for the coupling reaction. In addition, the spacer arm must be devoided off the folded conformations within its own structure which may be due to any one or all of the π -interactions, hydrogen bonding or dipole-dipole interactions as a long spacer arm with folded conformation may result in a poor synthesis. This fact has been discussed by several workers^{73,74,76-78} in detailed studies. They found a moderate increase in stepwise and final product yields by increasing the length of the spacer as well as the number of intervening atoms between two carbonyl groups. However, this effect is particularly visible when longer chains of oligomers are synthesized on silica-based supports where some of the reactive groups are buried inside the pores which are not exposable for the bulkier reagents. The spacer with a length of more than 25 atoms with fully extended conformation has been found to be the most useful one. Scheme 6 shows the spacer arm of commercially available long-chain alkylamine-controlled pore glass with nucleoside.

Scheme 6. Long chain alkylamine-controlled pore glass linked to leader nucleoside.

Support functionalization

Essentially two approaches have been followed for preparing functionalized polymer supports. The first one is based on the polymerization of a suitably functionalized monomer to produce homogeneously distributed functional groups in polymer supports, especially in case of organic supports. In the second one, most commonly used procedure, is the introduction of functional groups on to the preformed polymeric structure, particularly for inorganic supports. The main advantage of the latter method is that the degree of functionalization can be controlled very effectively.

The first step in the functionalization⁷⁹ of silica-based supports requires the refluxing with 35% HCl for 3–4 h. The treatment is required to hydrolyze the strained Si–O–Si bonds and to remove adsorbed gases or foreign material so that large numbers of Si–OH groups are available for further functionalization process. This step is followed by treatment with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysi-

lane^{33,60,80-85}. Unreacted silanol functionalities are then capped with trimethylchlorosilane (TMS-Cl). Other routes are also available for aminopropylation of silica-based supports. Fig. 1 shows the diagram of functionalization of glass support.

Fig. 1. Functionalization of silica based polymer supports.

Assessment of polymer capacity

The term 'polymer capacity' gives an estimate of the concentration of functional groups introduced during polymerization or post-polymerization manipulation. In other words, it provides an approximation of the reactive groups on the polymer support for further derivatization. As polymer capacity is related to the loading of the reactive groups on the support, it is defined in terms of mEq/g of support. The polymer capacity can be determined by both physical and chemical methods. Although chemical methods are slow and time-consuming as compared to physical ones, even so, these are quite oftenly being used. The physical methods which are rapid non-destructive include infrared (IR) spectroscopy⁸⁶⁻⁹⁰, ultraviolet (UV) spectroscopy^{35,91,92}, and nuclear magnetic

TABLE 2—METHODS FOR ESTIMATION OF THE CONCENTRATION OF FUNCTIONAL GROUPS ON POLYMER SUPPORTS

Sl. no.	Functional group	Reagents	Released chromophores	λ_{max} nm
1.	Amino	Ninhydrin	Indoxyl	570
		2,4,6-Trinitrobenzene sulfonic acid	Ammonium-2,4,6-trinitrobenzene sulfonate	250
		<i>N</i> -Succinimidyl-4- <i>O</i> -(4,4'-dimethoxytrityl)-butyrate (SDTB)	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
		3-Sulfo-SDTB	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
		4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl chloride (DMTrCl)	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
		<i>N</i> -Succinimidyl-3-(2-pyridyldithio)propionate (SPDP)	2-Thiopyridone	304
2.	Carboxyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenoxide	405
		2,4-Dinitrophenol	2,4-Dinitrophenoxide	415
		1- <i>O</i> -(4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl)-5-amino-1-pentanol (DTAP)	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
3.	Hydroxyl	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl chloride (DMTrCl)	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
		4- <i>O</i> -(4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl)hydroxybutyric acid (DHBA)	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
4.	Mercapto	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl chloride (DMTrCl)	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
		<i>N</i> -Succinimidyl-3-(2-pyridyldithio)propionate (SPDP)	Pyridine-2-thione	304
		2,2'-Dithiobis(5-nitropyridine) (DTNP)	5-Nitropyridine-2-thione	386
		4,4'-Dimethoxytrityloxy- <i>S</i> -(2-thio-5-nitropyridyl)-2-mercaptoethane (DTNPME)	4,4'-Dimethoxytrityl cation	498
		5,5'-Dithionitrobenzoic acid (DTNB)	5-Thionitrobenzoic acid	365

resonance (NMR)⁹³⁻⁹⁶ (¹H, ¹³C, metal ion *etc.*).

Chemical methods which are extensively being used can be classified further as (i) methods based on elemental analysis^{29,90,97}, (ii) methods based on acid-base titration^{98,99}, and (iii) methods based on the reactions of functional groups^{90,100-113}, i.e. functional groups present on the polymeric substance are reacted with a group specific reagent which in the subsequent step is released from the support and estimated by physical means to give the concentration or polymer capacity. There are several reagents available for the estimation of functional groups by chemical methods. The functional groups include amino, carboxyl, hydroxyl and mercapto. Some of them are listed in Table 2.

Different functionalities, viz. aminoalkyl, carboxyl, hydroxyl, mercaptoalkyl *etc.* on polymer supports have been employed for the derivatization of polymer supports required for the synthesis of oligonucleotides. A range of reagents have been developed for the estimation and determination of these functionalities on support as described in Table 2.

Linkages used for anchoring leader nucleoside

The methodology for the solid phase synthesis of oligonucleotides via established phosphoramidite approach requires anchoring of leader nucleoside on to the polymer support. Since most of the syntheses have been carried out from 3'-5' direction, the 3'-terminal of the leader nucleoside is attached to the support with a suitable linkage (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Attachment of leader nucleoside to polymer support.

Several linkages have been proposed for this purpose, viz. ester¹¹⁴, carbonate^{73,115}, carbamate^{73,116}, succinate^{33,59,67,76,117-127} and oxalyl¹²⁸. A large number of methods have been developed for attachment of the nucleosides via these linkages. Ideally, the selection of a particular linkage should be based on the following characteristics: (i) it should be stable during the functionalization as well as chain elongation, and (ii) it should easily be cleavable with mild reagents. The stability of some of the linkages reported in order of reactivity are: succinate < carbonate < carbamate, and it is now well-

established that there is no significant difference in the purity and yields of the final product on changing the support linkage.

Katzhendlar *et al.*⁷³ used *o*-nitrophenyloxycarbonyl chloride for the introduction of carbamate linkage between nucleoside and polymer support, whereas in another approach¹¹⁶ the commercially available reagent, tolylene-2,6-diisocyanate, has been used for the same purpose. However, this linkage could not find much applications as it requires 48 h treatment with aq. ammonia at elevated temperature to cleave the oligomer from the support. Similarly carbonate linkage has been introduced by several workers. Eritja *et al.*¹¹⁵ reported the synthesis of oligomers using nucleosides anchored on to the polymer support with this linkage. The introduction has been achieved by using a base labile 2-(2-nitrophenyl)ethyl linkage which can be cleaved under mild conditions by β -elimination and is found particularly suitable for base-modified oligomers. Despite the lability of the linkage to basic impurities in the solvents, the succinate linkage remains the most preferred one for routine synthesis of oligonucleotides.

The conventional method for the attachment of nucleosides to polymer supports involves the preparation of nucleoside-3'-*O*-succinates and their covalent anchoring on the supports. Essentially, two approaches¹²¹⁻¹³¹ are used for this purpose; the first one is based on the usage of activated nucleoside succinates while in the second, succinylation is performed on amino groups containing polymer support which in turn is coupled with the free 3'-hydroxyl function of the appropriately protected nucleosides using condensing agents. The latter method also obviates the conventionally employed time-consuming and cumbersome preparation of four nucleoside succinates which is also associated with the purification step over silica gel column chromatography. However, the preparation of these intermediates is no longer a limiting step, as Kumar *et al.*¹²² reported expeditious method for the synthesis of nucleoside-3'-*O*-succinates. Based on their observations, it does not make much difference in the time of functionalization procedure. They have precisely discussed the effects of various parameters like the concentration of succinic anhydride and dimethylaminopyridine and the effect of temperature and solvents, which affect the rate of succinylation of nucleosides. They further suggested that an *N*-acylpyridinium salt formed during the reaction between succinic anhydride and DMAP¹³² exists as loose ion-pairs in non-polar solvents which facilitates the nucleophilic attack as the acyl group by the amino groups of the polymer supports. Deoxynucleosides are succiny-

lated in just 10 min at 50° whereas ribonucleosides take 55 min. The longer time required in the ribo-series can be attributed to the steric crowding caused by 2'-O-TBDMS group. Additionally, the method does not require further purification of succinates. Attachment of appropriately protected nucleoside-3'(2')-O-succinates has been achieved generally by use of condensing reagents, dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) or DEC. Pon *et al.*¹¹⁸ demonstrated the usefulness of the condensing reagent, DEC/DMAP, for direct coupling of nucleoside-

succinates to amino group containing LCAA-CPG. The different methods of attachments of leader nucleosides to polymer supports are provided schematically in Scheme 7.

Alternatively, Damha *et al.*¹¹⁹ utilized the same condensing reagent to couple appropriately protected 2'-deoxyribo-, ribo- and arabinonucleosides to alkylamido-propionic acid-CPG via their 2'- or 3'-hydroxyl groups. Their method yielded reasonable good nucleoside loadings on the support and skipped the preparation of four

Scheme 7. Methods for attachment of leader nucleoside to polymer supports.

nucleoside succinates; however, the total time taken for the functionalization of the support was still too long (30 h).

In another approach, Sharma *et al.*¹³³ made use of a reactive bifunctional reagent, succinoyl chloride for anchoring nucleosides onto the aminoalkylated-CPG in one-pot method. Succinoyl chloride was converted to bis-triazolide followed by sequential addition of appropriately protected nucleoside and LCAA-CPG to furnish the functionalized support with moderate nucleoside loadings (30–32 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ of support). However, the moisture-sensitive nature of succinoyl chloride limits its use for routine functionalization of polymer supports. Efimov *et al.*¹³⁴ employed a bifunctional reagent, dipentafluorophenyl carbonate, for anchoring nucleoside succinates via the formation of pentafluorophenyl active ester, to the amino group containing polymer supports in 6–7 h with the nucleoside loadings range 30–50 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ of support. Two homobifunctional reagents, aryl- and alkyldiisocyanate have been employed by Kumar *et al.*¹²² for anchoring nucleoside succinates to polymer supports using hypernucleophilic, 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) as a catalyst. The functionalization process completes within 6 h at room temperature to give fully functionalized polymer supports with excellent nucleoside loadings. In a subsequent report, Kumar *et al.*^{124,125} appreciably reduced the total functionalization time to just 30 min at room temperature. In this study, the coupling of nucleoside succinates to amino group containing supports has been achieved by oxidation-reduction condensation process (Scheme 8). They used various oxidants and reductants and varied the solvents to optimize the results. DTNP/TPP was found to be the most versatile redox couple which worked very well in acetonitrile to obtain very high nucleoside loadings. The additional features include that the proposed method does not require absolute anhydrous conditions and hence commonly available solvents can be applied, and due to the fast reaction kinetics, they have carried out functionalization process in an automated DNA synthesizer keeping the coupling time of 2 min and obtained nucleoside loadings in the range of 27–30 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ LCAA-CPG. The method could be of interest for the functionalization of supports for rare or unusual nucleosides.

Scheme 8. Oxidation-reduction condensation method for attachment of nucleosides to polymer support.

In an attempt to synthesize oligomers with base sensitive *O*-alkylphosphotriesters or with intact *N*-acyl protecting groups, Alul *et al.*¹²⁸ demonstrated the utility of oxalyl linker.

Supports for modified oligonucleotide synthesis

Besides the synthesis of unmodified oligomers, recent trends have shown a preference for the support-based methods to synthesize 3'-end modified oligomers¹³⁵. Since most of the syntheses are now carried out on solid supports, the methodology for 3'-modifications involves the use of engineered polymer supports, which after the synthesis and final deprotection yield groups such as phosphate^{136–146}, aminoalkyl^{147–152}, thiol^{143,152–160}, thiophosphate^{143,154,155}, acridinyl, cholesteryl^{156,161–163}, etc. bearing oligonucleotides in either protected or unprotected form. Designer supports^{165–169} for the preparation of peptide-oligonucleotide conjugates have also been reported.

Supports for 3'-phosphorylation :

3'-Phosphorylated oligonucleotides are finding a variety of applications in molecular biology and related fields, e.g. for chemical ligation, structural studies, incorporation of modifications at internucleotidic linkages etc. Fig. 3 shows some of the engineered supports to generate oligonucleotide-3'-phosphates.

Fig. 3. Supports for the synthesis of 3'-phosphorylated oligonucleotides.

A useful chemical method based on sulfone linker with hydroxyethyl group on CPG support has been proposed by Markiewicz and Wyrzykiewicz¹³⁶. After synthesis, the support is treated with aq. ammonia to release the 3'-phosphorylated oligomer by β -elimination. Another method is based on the oxidation of *cis*-diol group of a ribonucleoside attached at the 3'-end, followed by base induced β -elimination to generate phosphorylated oligomers. In a different approach, 4,4'-dimethoxytrityloxyethylthiopropylated-CPG was used for oligonucleotide synthesis which was found to be stable under the condi-

tions employed during oligonucleotide synthesis via phosphoramidite approach. The phosphorylated oligonucleotides were obtained after treating the support with 50 mM dithiothreitol in aq. ammonia (29%) at 55° for 16 h. One of the most simplest methods for the synthesis of oligonucleotide-3'-phosphates employs the use of LCAA-CPG support. The desired material is generated by treatment with 80% aq. acetic acid.

Supports for 3'-aminoalkylation :

Some of the linker molecules used in the derivatization of polymer supports for the synthesis of 3'-aminoalkylated oligomers are depicted in Fig. 4. Most of the methods reported so far for this purpose require special deprotec-

Fig. 4. Supports for the synthesis of 3'-aminoalkylated oligonucleotides.

tion conditions. Essentially two strategies have been adopted for the designing and post-synthetic labeling of 3'-aminoalkyl group containing oligonucleotides via solid phase route : (i) direct incorporation of a reported group during support functionalization, and (ii) introduction of a masked aminoalkyl linked to the support. After oligonucleotide synthesis and deprotection, the reactive group is available for labeling purposes. In another approach, oligodeoxyribonucleotides were assembled on a ribonucleoside support, which upon oxidation with sodium periodate generated 3'-dialdehyde moiety. In the subsequent step, 3'-aminoalkylated oligonucleotides were obtained after reductive amination with hexamethylenediamine. In such a way the approach can be used to couple a variety of amino group bearing ligands such as intercalating agents, peptides and other fluorescent substances.

Supports for 3'-mercaptoalkylation :

In the very first report, Zuckermann *et al.*¹⁵⁷ demonstrated polymer support based synthesis of 3'-mercaptoalkylated oligonucleotides. However, the method involves the laborious functionalization of polymer support and also an extra nucleotidic base was added to the probe that was in a position to base pair which might cause mis-hybridization of oligonucleotide. Some of the support based methods for thiolation are given in the Fig. 5. The major advantage of having sulfhydryl group at 3'-terminal of synthetic oligonucleotides is that the group can be manipulated under mild conditions even under physiological conditions with high specificity and selectivity.

Fig. 5. Supports for the synthesis of 3'-mercaptoalkylated oligonucleotides.

Universal supports

In the recent past, attempts have been made to cut short the time of functionalization of polymer supports. However, one still needs to prepare all the four supports. To obviate the preparation of eight different polymer

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of a universal polymer support.

supports for DNA and RNA syntheses, Gough *et al.*^{169,170} designed a universal glass support (Fig. 6). Their approach basically depends on the attachment of a ribonucleoside (preferably uridine) through its 5'-terminal to polymer support with 2'(3')-O-benzoyl ester which allows the synthesis to be from 3'(2')-terminal. The release of ribonucleotide from the support is effected by conc. ammonium hydroxide-pyridine (2 : 1) for 16 h at 50°, whereas the release of oligodeoxyribonucleotide requires conc. ammonium hydroxide for 24 h at 60–65°.

Recently, the functionalization of the above described universal support was further simplified and achieved in automated DNA synthesizer by preparing a modified adapter¹⁷¹, e.g. 2'(3')-*O*-dimethoxytrityl-3'(2')-*O*-benzoyluridine-5'-*O*-(cyanoethyl-*N,N*-diisopropylphosphoramidite) (Fig. 7) and coupled to a standard T-support following standard phosphoramidite approach. The

Fig. 7. Adaptor for preparation of universal polymer support.

functionalized support was subsequently used for the synthesis of the desired oligonucleotide. The cleavage of oligoribonucleotide was achieved with pyridine-conc. ammonium hydroxide treatment for 24 h at 50° and the oligodeoxynucleotide with conc. ammonia for 48 h at 65°. Both of the supports are universal in a sense that they do not require all the four supports.

Of late, a universal support¹⁷² containing 1-*O*-(4,4'-dimethoxytrityl)-2-*O*-succinyl-3-*N*-allyloxycarbonylpropane (Fig. 8) has been proposed for the synthesis of oligonucleotides. Cleavage of the oligonucleotides from the support and removal of protecting groups have been

Fig. 8. Schematic representation of a non-nucleosidic universal polymer support.

accomplished in three steps, viz. (i) removal of allyl group, (ii) cleavage from the support, and (iii) removal of the protecting groups. Recently, a universal support (Fig. 9) has been proposed^{173,174} for the synthesis of oligodeoxynucleotides. Different deprotection conditions for the cleavage of oligonucleotides from the universal support have been discussed.

Fig. 9. Universal polymer support for the synthesis of oligodeoxynucleotides.

Concluding remarks

Advances in support functionalization have given greater freedom to effect the spread of preformed inor-

ganic polymeric structures based on silicious matrices as it has been possible with lesser efforts to control the degree of functionalization effectively. The chemistry of the synthesis of oligonucleotides is now well established and has proven the test of time. As the individual requirements are in minute quantities, the solid phase support system has taken over the synthesis from the solution phase operations; the system is easy to control and provides higher molecular conversions, thereby minimizing the usage of expensive starting materials. Because of repetitive nature of operation, the procedures have been enormously automated by optimizing the use of the polymeric support materials; the two polymer support materials based on controlled pore glass and polystyrenes respectively, both individually and independently have taken over the use of other support systems because of several advantages. The pore size in the solid phase synthesis mode has also been optimized and currently most of the automated machines use both controlled pore glass-based supports as well as polystyrene-based materials. The developments in the selection of spacer arms during the last one decade have also been phenomenal; in the early days, the utility of spacer arms was not well understood which often affected the quality of the final oligomer; but with increased understanding of the role of maintaining optimum distance from the polymer support, the process was standardized to the use of 20–25 atoms spacer arm which has been responsible for the smooth operation during synthesis. Orchestration and optimization in all these parameters have been responsible for making the synthesis simpler, and this has taken away much of the woe of the non-chemist users who are utilizing their own synthetic oligonucleotides by assembling them in automated gene machines routinely with as much effectively and ease as the specialized chemists.

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